

Identification of Fragments of 4Q26 (4QLev^d) and 4Q115 (4QDan^d)

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The Qumran Cave 4 manuscripts 4Q26 and 4Q115 are two of a small number of Dead Sea Scrolls manuscripts where, due to some chemical process involving the ink, the parchment has degraded. The most extreme cases are, aside from 4Q26 and 4Q115, the Cave 1 Genesis Apocryphon and 4Q406. Other, less extreme cases are 4Q11 and 4Q17, and perhaps even 4Q469. For the Cave 1 Genesis Apocryphon Ira Rabin has analyzed that the ink contained copper which, when exposed to UV light, catalyzes the degradation of the parchment (Elgvin 2016:283; Kottsieper 2019). The other manuscripts with similar degradation have not been tested and the explanations are less technical and specific. For example, Frank Moore Cross states about 4Q17: “The script has almost vanished from the surface of the leather, partially washed away, and partially eaten away, The ink used by the ancient scribe has etched the leather over the centuries, presumably because of some residual acid in the ink from its storage in a metal inkwell (Ulrich 1994:133). For 4Q26 Emanuel Tov described: “the ink has corroded and eaten through the leather, often creating the impression of a photographic negative. In some places the leather itself has disintegrated” (Ulrich 1994:133). The editors of 4Q11 observe, quoting McLean (1982:66) that “since the ink apparently contained iron, ‘many letters have been etched away due to the deterioration of the ink and the resulting acid compounds’” (Skehan 1992:18).

Due to the degradation of the parchment and the loss of many letters, the assignment of some of the fragments to one of those manuscripts is sometimes uncertain. The edition of 4Q115 included three fragments (10-12) “that may belong to this manuscript” and four more (frags. 13-16) “from other manuscripts” (Ulrich 2000, 279). The new photographs available on the Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library (www.deadseascrolls.org.il), make it possible to reassign some of those fragments that were published as 4Q26 and 4Q115.

1. 4Q115 frag. 14 reassign to 4Q26 (Lev 15:11-12)

Photographs:

PAM 43.084 <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284886>

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-367548>

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-367549>

The fragment was included in the edition of 4Q115 since it was found on the Museum plate no 1122 with 4Q115 fragments. However, the editor correctly discerned that the fragment was from another manuscript.

The remaining letters of line 2 can easily be matched to Lev 15:12, and the traces of line would fit קרר of Lev 15:11. One may transcribe

]ו[ח]פ[1
כ]ל[י] עץ ישן טף במים	2

If one follows the order of the biblical text, then the fragment, which should be assigned to 4Q26, originates from between 4Q26 frag. 2 (Lev 14:33-36) and 4Q26 frag. 3 (Lev 15:20-24).

Materially, the fragment (4Q115 frag. 14) is very much alike 4Q26 frag. 3, both being characterized by multiple wavy horizontal lines in the leather (as a result of the scratching of the skin?). Very similar lines on the skin are also found on 4Q115 frags. 15 and 16, and on the basis of their material appearance these should also be reassigned to 4Q26.

screen capture from <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-367549>

2. 4Q26 frag. 5 reassign to 4Q115 (Dan 10:1-2)

Photographs

PAM 42.635 <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284046> (with 4Q115)

PAM 43.040 <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284281> (with 4Q26)

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-295561>

The photographic record shows that the fragment was first placed with 4Q115 fragments, and subsequently with 4Q26 fragments, with which it has been published. The remaining letters, especially the clearly legibly שצר and מראה show that the fragment belongs to 4Q115.

○○○○○	1
בְּלֹא־שֹׁצֵר וְאִמְתַּת הַדְּבָר	2
בְּמֵרָאָה בְּיָמֵי הַהֵם	3

Strangely, no other traces are visible on the parchment, neither to the left nor to the right of this text. On the assumption that these letters have faded away without leaving traces or deteriorating the parchment, one might reconstruct the missing part of Dan 10:1 as follows:

]oooo[1
[בְּלִטְאִשְׁצֵר וְאִמַּת הַדְּבָר	2
[וְצַבָּא גְדוּל וּבִין אֵת הַדְּבַר וּבִינָה לּוּ [בְּמֵרָאָה בִּימֵי הֵהֱמָה	3

section from the fragment,
capture from <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-295561>

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